

High Professionalisation, Low Participation? Comparing the Role of Members in Economic and Non-economic EU-level Interest Groups

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Abstract

This article addresses the role played by members of interest groups in their groups' activities and lobbying. One characteristic of interest groups today is stronger professionalisation. In order to actively and efficiently advocate the interests of their members in EU policymaking, interest groups are relying ever more on their staff. Interest group scholars argue that, as a consequence, members are becoming structurally distant from their groups as their role becomes less important. However, what remains unknown is how this increasing professionalisation affects the role of members in different types of organisations. To address this research gap, we analyse the role played by members in economic and non-economic interest groups. We argue that professionalisation has a negative impact on members' role especially in non-economic interest groups, which is problematic because the professionalisation of these groups has been supported by EU institutions holding the ambition to make the EU more democratic but have in fact created an adverse effect.

Keywords

Interest groups; professionalization; members; democratic deficit; European Union

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Introduction

One of the biggest, ongoing criticisms facing the European Union (EU) today is the democratic deficit. As the sole EU institution directly representing the citizens and despite the changes brought by the Lisbon Treaty, the European Parliament still holds less power in decision-making processes than either the European Commission or the Council of the EU. This occurs while the EU and its institutions remain quite distant from the citizens of Europe (Saurugger, 2007: 387), and the idea of European integration may be quite abstract for them (De Clerck-Sachsee, 2012: 304).

Despite the European Parliament building up political power in recent years, voter turnout at European Parliament elections has been continuously falling since the first direct elections held in 1979, except for 2019, when voting turnout increased to 51% (European Union, 2024). As a result, European citizens do not share a common European identity, lack knowledge about EU public policies, do not always find the EU to be a good thing, and participate less at the EU level than at the national level. The 2024 Spring Eurobarometer showed that only 44% of the EU citizens held a positive attitude toward the EU (Eurobarometer, 2024).

The EU decided to face up to the democratic deficit criticism by encouraging the public's participation in EU policymaking and increasing the political legitimacy of EU policies (Kohler-Koch, 2009: 48; Mahoney and Beckstrand, 2011: 1343). After all, democratic processes are meaningless without citizens participating in public policymaking (Dalton, 2008: 78). During the 1990s, the European Commission and the European Council set out to design a clear strategy for including the public in policymaking processes (Lundberg and Sedelius, 2014: 323) to ensure that all groups have equal access to decision-makers. This consists of public consultations at the European Commission, the European citizens' initiative, petitions to the European Parliament as well as financial grants from the European Commission to different stakeholders that seek to ensure the legitimacy of both policy outcomes and policymaking participation (Mahoney and Beckstrand, 2011: 1341).

In 2016, the European Commission initiated a better regulation policy, with the aim to increase transparency, strengthen democratic and evidence-based policy making that consist of public consultations, regulatory impact assessments, as well as evaluations (Bunea and Chrisp, 2023). Yet, there is empirical evidence of different engagement with EU policymaking among different types of stakeholders. Economic interests are mostly represented at the EU level, yet non-economic interests that usually represent public interests remain underrepresented in EU policymaking and are thus in need of encouragement from the EU for stronger involvement (Saurugger, 2008: 1283).

Despite the encouragement and opportunity structures available to interest groups, EU institutions do not enable equal access to all actors wishing to impact EU policies, while open consultations are far from being inclusive and transparent (Quittkat, 2011), making informal networking more successful (Peterson and Bomberg, 2003: 324, 328). The Commission generally considers only interest groups displaying high levels of institutionalisation and professionalisation and employing experts in individual policy areas (Mahoney and Beckstrand, 2011).

EU-level umbrella organisations and bigger interest groups, with greater resources and better expertise, are more successful in accessing both decision-makers (Berkhout and Lowery, 2011; Mahoney and Beckstrand, 2011: 1358; Sanchez Salgado, 2014: 350) and the national groups (Hanegraaff and van der Ploeg, 2020). Furthermore, by comparison to economic interest groups, citizens and non-economic groups are less informed about opportunities for participation in EU policymaking (Bunea and Chrips, 2023). To be able to equally participate in EU policymaking, interest groups thus need to professionalise their organisational activities, which often leads to weaker connections with their members since interest group staff make most of the decisions and groups

concentrate more on advocacy activities than servicing their members (Maloney, 2007: 70; Beyers, Eising and Maloney, 2008: 118).

This creates a unique dilemma, as professionalisation prevents smaller, unorganised, and less professional groups from becoming part of EU public policymaking – even if they are politically active (Heidbreder, 2012: 10). While, on one side, civil society movements, less institutionalised and smaller nongovernmental organisations are left out of the policymaking process, on the other, the non-economic interest groups that become professionalised so as to be included in policymaking are failing to socialise their members and supporters. Even though interest groups may be able to bring the meaning of the EU closer to their members, to be able to do that they must be willing and capable of providing political education. When these groups focus more on advocacy activities than on supporting their members, the role of political education typically becomes neglected. Interest group activity expands the influence of citizens' participation beyond elections and enhances general political participation (Dalton, 2008: 94) and thus represents a valuable alternative to participation at elections. However, as Warleigh (2001: 623) states regarding democratisation of the EU, interest groups that include members in their decision-making should have access to EU decision-makers.

In this article, we understand interest groups as organised, politically active and not competing at elections (Beyers et al, 2008). They have some sort of constituency in either the form of supporters or members and represent their members' interests or the interests of others who are unable to represent themselves. These groups are either occasionally or permanently interested in policymaking processes. This includes business groups, trade unions, societies and religious groups. These associations entail very different types of organisations with a different "logic of membership" (Schmitter and Streeck, 1999). Interest groups with individual members play the role of transmission belts of the people's voice to EU-decision makers. They provide their members with social capital, bring up the issue of democracy and represent non-economic, general interests. These are cause, identity or leisure groups. On the other hand, economic interests active in the business sector, such as business associations, employers' associations as well as trade unions and professional associations, represent economic interests often understood as representing selfish economic interests (Beyers et al, 2008: 1109-1111). Although important, the participation of the membership in these organisations' decision-making in general is not related to the issue of democracy (Kohler-Koch, 2010).

Scholars have assumed that to be able to influence EU policymaking, effectively represent their members and strengthen EU democracy, interest groups must become more professional. This requirement for non-economic interest groups is reflected in the biased interest representation in Brussels, where economic groups are in the majority. However, the professionalisation of interest groups is believed to have negative impacts, such as declining democratic participation, whereby members are no longer included in the interest group's activities and the majority of decisions are made by staff working for the group. The assumption that professionalisation jeopardises democratic participation in terms of giving members less of a voice in interest group activities lacks empirical analysis. In this article, we therefore wish to examine whether the effects of professionalisation on members' inclusion in interest group activities are the same irrespective of the way interest groups are organised.

We continue the article with a literature review on the effects of professionalisation on the role of the membership, an overview of members' inclusion in interest group activity, and an analysis of the influence of professionalisation on the democratic modes of decision-making in interest groups. In the conclusion, we sum up the main findings.

Professionalisation's impacts on members' role in interest group activity

Interest groups bring added value to decisions made at the EU level since they represent a plurality of interests, values and desires. They possess broader and more general knowledge and information useful for European officials and experts. In contrast to EU officials, interest groups work more across sectors and cover broader policy areas (Kohler-Koch, 2009: 50). At the same time, interest groups accumulate technical and expert information in specific areas that public officials lack when it comes to preparing legislative proposals that are technically implementable and politically feasible. For this reason, interest groups represent a key actor in participatory and evidence-based policymaking tools implemented by the European Commission (Bunea and Chrips, 2023). There are two main reasons for interest groups to include their members more in group activities: political socialisation and education for better political participation; and the representation of different opinions in policymaking. The more diverse and numerous the interest group arena, the better the society and the democracy. Interest groups should, beside influencing the legislative outcomes of public policies, politically educate their members about policy problems and activities while permitting their members to play an active role in formulating the interest group's positions on policy issues (Warleigh, 2001: 623).

The inclusion of interest groups in EU policymaking allows the EU to move closer to particular social groups. The idea is that non-economic interest groups which advocate the citizens' interests act as a bridge between European citizens and decision-makers in EU institutions, facilitate public discourse between the state and the citizens, and help transmit information between both parts (Warleigh, 2001: 620, 622). At the same time, citizens' active participation by way of engagement in non-economic interest groups promotes democratic participation. The close collaboration of non-economic interest groups and EU institutions should thereby help cut the democratic deficit and increase social cohesion and trust by way of: 1) effective representation; 2) advocating a policy outcome that is preferred by citizens; and 3) producing a better democracy with the political education of members through civic experiences (Maloney, 2009: 278). Regardless of the type of interest group, their structural features or local context, they contribute to the building up of social capital (Maloney et al, 2008).

Given certain conditions, interest groups have a development impact on their members by helping citizens develop political skills, civic virtues and critical skills (Warren, 2001). Participation in interest group activities improves the social skills of their members, develops their pro-social values and norms, while assisting them in becoming involved in various networks that also facilitate citizens' engagement and participation in democratic politics (Maloney et al, 2008: 276). Membership in interest groups also influences members' everyday life. Survey results show that interest group members evaluate interest groups as important in their lives and comparable to the importance of their family and friends. Their trust in office holders and other interest group members is high (Maloney et al, 2008: 270-271).

However, policymaking has today become professionalised and demands expertise and technical knowledge (Maloney, 2009: 282), which is leading to changes in the organisation of interest groups and their relationship with their members. Interest groups are forced to act professionally if they want to adapt to changed conditions in Brussels, access the decision-makers, enhance their lobbying capacity (Albareda, 2020; Klüver and Saurugger, 2013: 186; Kohler-Koch and Buch, 2013), and better advocate the interests of their members (Maloney, 2007: 70; Beyers et al, 2008: 118). Indeed, decision-makers tend to consider those interest groups that are the most coherent, compelling and convincing (Maloney, 2007: 71). Many interest groups have thus professionalised themselves and transformed into protest-business-type organisations (Jordan and Maloney, 1998).

The trend of interest groups' professionalisation can be noticed in all developed countries, not just in the EU. In newer democracies like Central and Eastern Europe professionalization of interest groups can be understood as addition to democratisation and is dependent funding sources, cooperation with other organisations, and interest groups position in the domestic interest group system contributes to professionalization of interest groups (Dobbins et al, 2022). The volunteer-based organisations have been replaced by professionally managed organisations, often even without a membership base (Skocpol, 2004). It is characteristic that such interest groups are organised according to hierarchical business principles (Maloney, 2009: 278), are professionalised, bureaucratic and have full-time paid staff (Maloney, 2009: 278), with in-house lobbyists, scientists, PR staff and professional management and fund-raising activities (Maloney, 2007: 71). When necessary, they engage external experts to cover specific topics and for communication work. At the same time, they build on their extensive knowledge based on research and consulting activities and try to mobilise their members through use of modern communication media. However, communication with members simply through social media and the Internet does not enable genuine communication, an exchange of opinions and rational arguments (Kohler-Koch and Buch, 2013). The meaning of membership, participation and civic virtue has consequently changed (Maloney, 2007: 75).

Hence, for logistical and practical reasons, these interest groups try to influence public policies without the input of their membership base. Interest groups find it more efficient when policy outcomes are influenced without having to involve their members (Maloney, 2009: 279). Servicing the membership also brings an additional cost for interest groups. Interest groups with limited resources thus prioritise effective policymaking over raising awareness among their members (Maloney, 2009: 279-280, 284), while members are no longer decisive in influencing EU policymaking (Jordan and Maloney, 2007: 11). Interest groups' campaigns, strategies, tactics and policies are formulated by staff without the influence of their members (Maloney, 2009: 278). Permanent staff enables continuity in an interest group's work, improves the independence of the leadership and offers a division of labour within that group. Previous research also shows that employees of EU-level organisations often possess international and European experiences as well as established contacts in the Brussels arena (Kohler-Koch and Buch, 2013).

Consequently, a high level of professionalisation weakens the connection between interest groups and their members (Maloney, 2007: 70; Beyers et al, 2008: 118). The interest group system is thus structurally distant from the supporters and members (Long and Lörinczi, 2009: 183). Their decision-making is insufficiently democratic, with most decisions taken in the organisation being formed by organisational staff and not corresponding to their members and supporters (Warleigh, 2001: 622-623). Interest groups help educate citizens about democratic decision-making only when they address internal issues in a democratic way (Liebert, 2009: 76). Instead, they contribute to producing more broadly acceptable policy outcomes more than they educate their members and supporters. Therefore, members are limited in their political involvement and end up primarily becoming just supporters who pay membership fees, also called "chequebook participation" (Maloney, 2009: 278). Besides donations, members engage in other individualistic activities like signing petitions, boycotting products and ethical shopping, but are not asked to commit to the organisation or engage in collective activities such as attending meetings, rallies and demonstrations (Maloney, 2009: 278; Kohler-Koch and Buch, 2013).

One of the most salient criticisms of the interest group system and its role at the EU level is thus the low level of members' political socialisation (Warleigh, 2001: 623). The internal leadership of such groups is often too elitist, preventing members from taking part in their organisational activities

(Warleigh, 2001: 635). Interest organisations at the EU level are more political actors than organisations providing services to their members (Greenwood, 2007: 347). Greenwood states (2003: 61-62) that this form of representation is in fact some kind of elite pluralism of organised civil society at the EU level, which does not allow the membership base to be actively included in formulating the organisation's positions, policies, campaigns and strategies (Long and Lörinczi, 2009: 183).

We encounter a paradox when, to more effectively represent their members, interest groups rely more on their staff than on their members, which in turn means that interest groups are becoming ever less representative (Heylen, 2018), while the quality of such representation is under question (Kohler-Koch and Buch, 2013). Highly professionalised staff leads to the more efficient work of interest groups, but this is often at the expense of the transparency and quality of participatory democracy (Kohler-Koch and Buch, 2013).

Another factor explaining members' low involvement in their interest group's activity is that members prefer to not become involved in political activities and prefer to make a financial contribution to the right cause (Maloney, 2009: 279). As Warleigh (2001: 635) warns, the majority of members are not prepared to take on an active role in the interest group's activities and are more attracted to limited involvement with the interest group (Maloney, 2007: 75). Passive involvement in the interest group's activities is often perceived as a benefit, while active involvement is seen as a cost since, besides the financial contribution, time is also regarded as a resource (Maloney, 2007: 76-77). After all, citizens often "do not want to make political decisions themselves" (Hibbing and Theiss-Morse, 2004: 1) and "can find better things to do with their time" (Maloney, 2009: 277). Yet Dalton (2008: 85) notes that, despite the low levels of political participation, citizens are seeking different, more direct ways of policymaking such as working with interest groups, political consumerism, political actions and so on.

What remains unclear is whether stronger professionalisation always leads such groups to have weaker connections with their members. Some studies have shown that more professionalised interest groups prefer that decisions are made by the interest groups management then by the membership (Bolleyer and Correa, 2022; Heylen et al, 2020). The role of the transmission belt and the promoter of democratic participation can be only held by non-economic interest groups that represent citizens' interests. On the other hand, economic interest groups mostly promote economic, corporate interests where the inclusion of members, although important, is not related to the issue of democracy. In the early years of the European integration, trade unions and business groups prevailed in Brussels since most EU policies were focused on the Common Market.

With the expansion of EU competences, the number of interest groups present in Brussels increased. Non-economic interest groups became a relevant actor in EU policymaking and were supported by the European Commission. It was the European Commission itself that often also initiated or even funded the formation of some EU-level groups (Kohler-Koch and Buch, 2013). Precisely with the support of EU institutions, over the years non-economic interest groups gained a stronger voice (Dür and Mateo, 2016). This was achieved with the professionalisation of non-economic groups. Klüver and Saurugger (2013) find that non-economic groups and economic groups are equally professionalised, among other reasons due to the pressure exerted by European institutions for them to organise themselves coherently while presenting their interests. However, it is precisely the professional non-economic interest groups that have failed to promote democratic participation (Kochler-Koch and Quittkat, 2013). Studies have shown that economic interest groups tend to include members more in their decision making than non-economic interest groups (Berkhout et al, 2021). Economic interests demonstrated that a higher level of professionalisation may also lead to an

association's greater responsiveness and accountability towards their members (Bouwen, 2006). Their common characteristic is that their members are predominantly companies and not individuals. Their potential members can be easily identified while their membership base is more homogeneous which makes it easier for determining the aims of the organisation, forming the interest group's position, and for including members in the group's activities (Beyers, 2008). It seems that the negative impact of professionalisation on the promotion of democratic participation only affects non-economic groups whose aim is to give citizens a voice. EU institutions' ambition to strengthen interest groups' inclusion in EU policymaking by way of professionalisation may thus bring an adverse effect.

In this article, we intend to answer our research question concerning whether professionalisation jeopardises democratic participation in terms of giving members less of a voice in the decision-making activities or whether it effects non-economic interest groups in particular. To help narrow the research gap on how the level of professionalisation and inclusion of the membership in interest group activities correlate depending on the organisational type of an interest group, we formulated two hypotheses:

H1) A higher level of professionalisation is associated with the use of less democratic modes of decision-making.

H2) Within interest groups at the same level of professionalisation, more democratic decision-making modes are used by economic interest groups than by non-economic interest groups.

The following section analyses the impacts of professionalisation on the level of democratic modes of decision-making.

Research data and methods

The analysis is based on data collected within the framework of the INTEREURO project (Beyers et al, 2014; Beyers et al, 2016; Beyers et al, 2020). A sample of the European interest community (i.e. 2,038³ EU peak associations or national organisations with a presence in Brussels) was invited to take part in a web survey. Since we are interested in the roles and activities assumed by members of non-economic interest groups in comparison to economic interest groups, we performed our analysis on 352 trade unions, trade, business and professional associations, and 296 non-governmental organisations, platforms, networks, and similar⁴. All organisations included in the analysis are membership-based organisations. We understand the term member broadly. For example, members may include regular donors who only make financial contributions as well as active members who are engaged in a wide range of organisational activities. Members can be individuals, firms or other organisations. The survey took place between March and June 2015. Most organisations have their headquarters in Belgium (478 organisations or 73.8%), indicating we are principally analysing EU-level groups.

We begin our analysis with an overview of activities undertaken by members in their interest group's functioning and employ descriptive analysis. We continue our research by comparing the level of professionalisation and levels of democratic modes of decision-making in interest groups in general and between different types of interest groups: economic and non-economic.

³ The survey includes the entire European interest community. Interest groups were selected from a sampling frame of entities listed in the *Transparency Register* of the European Union, the *OECKL Directory*, and during previous research projects related to Beyers et al (2014).

⁴ The analysis is performed on 648 cases. Due to missing answers on some of the variables, the number of organisations included in different analyses is lower.

The dependent variable in our analysis is *democratic decision-making in interest group activity*. We defined democratic decision-making as the mode of decision-making an interest group employs when making different decisions. Qualitative research shows that interest groups can use several democratic decision-making forms such as consensus among members through to less democratic forms: voting among members, consensus of the board, voting on the board, and the least democratic form where senior staff take the decision (Beyers et al, 2015)⁵. To form an index of democratic decision-making, we considered decision-making modes regarding the following interest group activities: (1) budget; (2) hiring staff; (3) changes to statutory rules or the constitution etc.; (4) establishing the organisation's position on policy issues; and (5) deciding on advocacy/lobbying strategies and tactics. Members can be included in certain types of decisions more than in others. We decided to include different activities to ensure a diversity between the interest groups in the inclusion of members in their activities.

In the analysis, we compare the level of democratic decision-making modes in interest groups with the level of professionalisation, which is operationalized as the number of paid staff in the organisation.⁶ Scholars use different variables as indicators of the level of professionalisation such as number of staff, year of establishment, and budget size (Chaqués and Muñoz, 2016). For our analysis, we decided to use the variable number of staff since the presence of staff in interest groups has the strongest influence on the role of members. In addition, the number of staff often correlates with the level of professionalisation.

Results

Members' role in interest group activity

In general, members can play an important role in the activity of interest groups. Besides professional staff, members are part of the organisation's human resources (Carmin, 2010: 187) since they can participate in mobilising activities while they may also possess useful technical information. A strong membership base contributes to the organisation's credibility and gives it more political power (Sissenich, 2010: 15). If an organisation has few members, it may be questionable whether it still represents the interest of broader society (Petrova, 2007: 1282) and whether it is representative.

Figure 1 shows that membership plays an important role in all activities. Members are least important in the running of local groups or branches, probably because just 161 groups also have local or regional chapters. Although members support interest groups and facilitate their activities by paying membership fees, the importance of members in generating the group's income is neither the highest nor more important than other activities. Based on a literature review on interest group

⁵ We formed a measure from decision-making modes where a consensus among members represents the most democratic decision-making mode with an assigned value of 4, followed by voting among members (value 3), consensus of the board (value 2), voting of the board (value 1) and senior staff take the decision (value 0). Decision-making modes to five variables concerning the activities of budget, hiring staff, changes to statutory rules or the constitution etc., establishing your organisation's position on policy issues and deciding on advocacy/lobbying strategies and tactics were computed to form an index of democratic decision-making. The index took values from 0 = least democratic decision-making for all interest group activities (0.2% of organisations) to 20 = most democratic decision-making for all interest group activities (3.5% of organisations).

⁶ The question wording was: How many paid staff (full-time equivalent) work in the following activities for your organisation? We transformed the answers into an ordinal scale with 4 intervals: Value 0 = no employees, 1 = one employee, 2 = 2 to 5 employees, 3 = 6 to 11 employees, 4 = 12 or more employees.

professionalisation that stresses members' role is limited to financial participation, we would expect that members are crucial in this activity. There are no differences between non-economic and economic groups regarding the importance of the members. Only for the activity of generating income are members of economic groups significantly more important than members of non-economic groups⁷. There are also no substantial differences between membership types. Interest groups with only individual members find their members less important for providing ideas about the organisation's campaign strategies⁸ and in identifying problems or supplying ideas about the activities⁹ in comparison to interest groups involving other types of membership.

Figure 1. Importance of the membership for EU-level organizations regarding certain activities.

Note: The figure represents mean values where 1 - Not at all important, 2 - Not very important, 3 - Neither important not unimportant, 4 - Important, 5 - Very important.

EU-level organisations recognise their members are some of the most important actors when it comes to making decisions about advocacy and lobbying tactics or forming the organisation's position. However, professional staff and management are even more influential. The organisational type affects the importance of the members. Non-economic groups rate the membership as being significantly less influential in deciding on advocacy and lobbying tactics and in forming the organisation's position on EU policies compared to organisations that are economic. This is probably

⁷ The mean value of the importance of members for generating income for non-economic groups is 4.1 while for economic groups it is 4.3 ($F=30.754$; sig. < 0.001).

⁸ The mean value of the importance of members for providing ideas about campaign strategies for interest groups with only individuals as members is 3.9 while for groups that also allow other types of members it is 4.2 ($F=4.588$; sig.<0.050).

⁹ The mean value of the importance of members for identifying problems or providing ideas for activities for interest groups with only individuals as members is 4.2 while for groups that also have other types of members it is 4.5 ($F=4.172$; sig<0.050).

connected with the membership type.¹⁰ Non-economic interest groups are more likely to have individuals as members; 48.8% of non-economic interest groups have individuals as members whereas only 18.2% of economic interest groups have individuals as members. The inclusion of individual members in interest groups' activities helps with more inclusive democracy, yet coordinating individuals and searching for a consensus among them is also more difficult than when seeking to coordinate members that are not individuals. Less influential actors prominent in EU-level interest groups in these two areas are charities and corporate sponsors, donors, beneficiaries and clients along with other advocacy and lobbying organisations. Although most of these actors give financial support to these organisations, they are less influential in establishing the organisation's position on EU policies and deciding on their strategies.

Figure 2. Actors' influence on the interest group's position on EU policies and on advocacy and lobbying tactics.

Note: The figure represents mean values where 1 - Not at all influential, 2 - Not very influential, 3 - Somewhat influential, 4 - Very influential.

¹⁰ The mean value of the influence of membership on forming the organisation's position on EU policies for economic groups is 3.3 and for non-economic groups it is 3.1 ($F=11.303$; $\text{sig}.<.0.001$). The mean value of the influence of membership in deciding about advocacy and lobbying for organisations without any individual members is 3.2 and for organisations with individual members it is 3.0 ($F=6.147$; $\text{sig}.<.0.050$).

Membership can also be an indicator for interest groups in terms of evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of their activities and processes: 31.9% of organisations evaluate their effectiveness and efficiency based on how many supporters they have, 46.3% on the number of supporters who renew their membership each year and 33.2% on the number of new supporters recruited each year.

Organisations are highly accountable to their membership. This contrasts with what Warleigh (2001: 631) established in interviews regarding the development and environmental sectors where interest groups found themselves accountable to client groups but not to their supporters. Our study shows that interest groups are almost equally accountable to the board of directors/executive committee. Also high on the scale are the chair of the board and executive director. Organisations are again less accountable to the actors that financially support them (charities and corporate sponsors, donors and beneficiaries and clients).

Figure 3. Accountability to different actors.

Note: The figure includes mean values where 1 - Not at all important, 2 - Not very important, 3 - Neither important nor unimportant, 4 - Important, 5 - Very important

The results thus far show that members are very important for interest groups. Members are more important for economic interest groups than for non-economic interest groups. We will continue by examining the effects of professionalisation on decision-making modes and the differences between economic and non-economic groups.

Professionalisation and democratic decision-making modes in interest groups

According to the literature review, stronger professionalisation weakens the connection between interest groups and their members. Members become less involved in the decision-making activities of their interest group. The analysis hitherto shows that members are regarded as important in different interest group activities also when compared with other actors involved in interest groups. Moreover, interest groups feel accountable to their members.

We continue our analysis by looking at the different ways of making decisions in interest groups. Interest groups can use more democratic decision-making modes such as consensus or by members voting or less democratic modes such as consensus or voting by the board or even where senior staff make all the decisions. To test our first hypothesis, namely, that a higher level of professionalisation is associated with use of less democratic decision-making modes, we performed a correlation test. The correlation is statistically significant with less than one per cent of risk. The value of Pearson's correlation coefficient is -0.278, showing a moderate downwards sloping, negative linear relationship. The more employed staff an interest group has, the less democratic are the modes of decision-making that are used. This confirms our first hypothesis that interest groups which are more professionalised apply less democratic decision-making modes.

The second hypothesis assumes that among interest groups at the same level of professionalisation it is economic interest groups which use more democratic modes of decision-making than non-economic groups. The reasoning behind this hypothesis is the view that the negative effects of professionalisation are mostly detectable in non-economic groups which also are more likely to have individuals as members. For logistical and practical reasons, interest groups which include individuals as members find it more difficult to include those members in the group's activities (see Maloney, 2007: 82). It is also easier for individuals to enter or leave an interest organisation if they change their mind, unlike other types of members such as businesses and national organisations that are more steady members. In addition, national organisations, companies and governments possess more expert and technical knowledge that may be useful to the interest group while lobbying and are included in decision-making for their knowledge and know-how (Heylen, 2018). It is also more plausible that individual members actually prefer not to be included in activities as that would impose an extra burden on them.

Our comparison of members' level of importance for different interest group types has already demonstrated that members are more important for economic groups. To compare the relationship between levels of professionalisation and levels of democratic decision-making modes for economic and non-economic groups, we first performed a correlation analysis. The results show a statistically significant correlation for economic and non-economic interest groups with less than one per cent risk. The correlation is, however, stronger for economic groups with the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient being -0.333 (in contrast to -0.266 for non-economic groups). This again shows a moderate downwards sloping, negative linear relationship whereby an increase in staff leads to a decrease in democratic modes of decision-making.

The results of a comparison of levels of democratic decision-making modes for the same levels of professionalisation by comparing mean values are presented in Table 1. The more professionalised

an interest group, the lower the level of democratic decision-making mode for both economic and non-economic groups. However, economic groups always have a higher level of democratic decision-making mode. This then confirms our second hypothesis that among interest groups at the same level of professionalisation it is economic groups that apply more democratic decision-making modes. While confirming our second hypothesis, this also reveals that professionalisation hinders the involvement of members in group activities for both non-economic and economic groups. Nevertheless, in terms of the political socialisation and EU's democratisation, it is important that individual citizens are enabled to become more involved in decision-making concerning the functioning of their interest group. For this reason, the generally less democratic decision-making modes seen among non-economic interest groups are particularly worrying.

Our analysis reveals another characteristic: interest groups without any employees apply less democratic decision-making modes than groups that employ at least one person. This is detected among both economic and non-economic groups. A low level of professionalisation seems to be beneficial for strengthening democracy within interest groups. It is likely that a single person employed full time by such an organisation to help with its activities has the capacity to coordinate and assist members by way of including them in the group's activities but is unable to also take on the organisation's decision-making alone.

Table 1. Comparison of mean values of democratic decision-making modes for economic and non-economic interest groups at different levels of professionalisation.

Type of organisation	Level of professionalisation	Level of democratic decision-making modes		
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Non-economic interest groups	0 no employees	9.97	35	3.81
	1 employee	11.53	34	2.70
	2 to 5 employees	9.29	67	3.78
	6 to 11 employees	8.35	20	2.74
	More than 12 employees	7.65	31	4.10
	Total	9.45	187	3.74
Economic interest groups	0 no employees	12.75	32	4.12
	1 employee	13.21	34	3.83
	2 to 5 employees	11.66	100	3.76
	6 to 11 employees	10.79	29	3.24
	More than 12 employees	8.62	39	4.04
	Total	11.42	234	4.04

Conclusion

The growing professionalisation of policymaking is occurring parallel to interest groups also becoming ever more professional. Policymakers need technical knowledge and expertise that can be provided by the specialists employed by interest groups. The European Commission also encourages this in the belief that making non-economic interest groups more professional will also ensure that more non-economic interest groups participate in EU policymaking. The inclusion of non-economic interest groups in policymaking gives the citizens a voice concerning decisions taken by EU institutions and reduces the EU's democratic deficit. When interest groups are seeking to recruit new staff, 59.3% of them find professional qualifications and expertise more important than applicants' understanding of and commitment to the organisational objectives. This means there is no longer any need for members' input. Members are thereby being left out of all decision-making processes in their interest group, with

their role being reduced to that of a financial supporter. However, the results of our analysis show that members continue to remain important in those EU-level interest groups which function in a more competitive environment. Namely, when defined broadly just like the professional staff, members can also be part of the organisation's human resources (Carmin, 2010: 187). Although EU-level organisations all see their membership as highly important, it is necessary to know how democratic is the decision-making that occurs in interest groups.

Democratic modes of decision-making are used less by interest groups that may be characterised as more professional and which have more employees. Professionalisation indeed hinders members' inclusion in decision-making processes. Although this impacts non-economic groups more, the effect is also seen among economic groups. Some scholars argue that the professionalisation of interest groups increases their efficiency. The representativeness of interest groups is also a question of the expertise interest groups hold, their credibility or their trust in their leadership (Buth, 2011). However, without internally democratic participation, interest groups can no longer perform the role of political socialisation. According to Dalton (2008: 94), citizens' participation in interest groups may be seen as an opportunity for better democratic participation.

Our analysis showed one exception to the notion that an increase in professionalisation leads to interest groups including members less in the group activities. The results of our analysis show that a minimum level of professionalisation in fact increases the level of democratic decision-making. Interest groups employing at one person apply more democratic decision-making modes than groups without any employees. It is thus important that an interest group strike a balance between professionalisation and the inclusion of members in its activities. An interest group can professionalise its activities to some degree and still include members in its activities. Warleigh's thesis (Warleigh, 2001) concerning elite decision-making in interest groups' activities might be somewhat excessive. Maloney (2009: 284) believes that, although members' involvement is shallow, this does not mean interest groups do not contribute to democracy since, after all, any participation "is seen as good" (Jordan and Maloney, 2007: 5). Moreover, Buth (2011) shows that supporters trust the leaders of their interest groups will represent their interest also based on their credibility and expertise without having to be directly involved in the organisation. These groups still perform the role of representativeness and contribute to the legitimacy of policymaking. In the future, it would be useful to look at how members are included in activities of interest groups at the national level where greater potential resides for citizens' political socialisation.

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